

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG
emission estimates

Cavity ring-down spectroscopy

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Cavity ring-down spectrometers can be used to measure the amount of different gases, including greenhouse gases CO_2 and CH_4 , in the air. For this, the air sample is placed between mirrors inside a cavity and a laser pulse with a specific wavelength is sent through it. It bounces back and forth between the mirrors and the rate of the decrease in intensity (“ring-down”) is measured. The rate of this decrease is correlated with the concentration of the measured compound. As different gases absorb at different wavelengths, their amounts can be distinguished by measuring with laser pulses of different wavelengths.

For NuClim, our colleagues from the Finnish Meteorological Institute use a cavity ring-down spectrometer to measure CO_2 , CO and CH_4 . Their instrument uses three mirrors to trap the laser pulse between them. They have it set up in their measurement container at Graciosa ENA station.

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